

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Pharmaceutical Removal from Wastewater by Adsorption on Commercial Materials and Molecularly Imprinted Polymers

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This study focused on the development of an adsorption/desorption process as effective technology for pharmaceutical removal from wastewater. The target pharmaceuticals selected are ibuprofen, diclofenac and carbamazepine, while the sorbent materials tested are two commercial ones, an activated carbon Norit 1240W, typically used in wastewater treatment [1], and the non-ionic resin XAD16N, as well as Molecularly Imprinted Polymers (MIPs). Firstly, a sorbent screening phase was conducted in batch mode showing the effectiveness of commercial sorbents and of one MIP for CBZ, that is MIP_CBZ_MAA_TRIM. Then, 3 continuous flow tests were performed with CBZ using the 3 most promising materials previously selected at the same operating conditions, that are Empty Bed Contact Time (EBCT) = 3 min and a bed height of about 20 cm. The breakthrough curves obtained are showed in Figure 1: the MIP for CBZ got saturated after only 3000 BVs, while Norit and XAD16N achieved a 20% breakpoint (BP) at about 18500 Bed Volumes (BVs) of treated wastewater; moreover, XAD16N showed a higher operating capacity (12.4 mg/g_{dry sorbent}) with respect to Norit (7.1 mg/g_{dry sorbent}), resulting in a very promising material. The possibility of in situ sorbent regeneration was studied testing the effectiveness of 3 different solvents that are methanol, ethanol and 2-propanol. The analysis revealed that XAD16N can be easily regenerated with 10 to 17 BVs of solvent, depending on the target micropollutant, and among the tested solvents, ethanol is the most promising in terms of consumption and efficiency. Eventually, this study demonstrated the effectiveness of XAD16N and Norit in removing pharmaceuticals from wastewater, with the possibility of *in-situ* regeneration of XAD16N with a very limited amount of ethanol. This work represents a relevant progress towards the development of a reliable and cost-effective adsorption/desorption process.

Figure 1: Carbamazepine breakthrough curves experimental data and best-fitting simulations performed with Aspen Adsorption.

References

[1] Benstoem, F., Nahrstedt, A., Boehler, M., Knopp, G., Montag, D., Siegrist, H., Pinnekamp, J., Performance of granular activated carbon to remove micropollutants from municipal wastewater - A meta-analysis of pilot- and large-scale studies. *Chemosphere*, 2017, **185**, 105–118.